
Sentinel-1 PSI data for the evaluation of landslide geohazard and impact

Silvia Bianchini, Lorenzo Solari, Anna Barra, Oriol Monserrat, Michele Crosetto, Filippo Catani

Abstract

In this work we exploited Sentinel-1 satellite radar images processed by means of Persistent Scatterers Interferometry (PSI) techniques for the evaluation of landslide geohazard and impact on a mountainous region. In particular, we used PSI data as starting point in a working chain whose final goal is the estimation of the potential worth of loss of the structures involved by slope instability phenomena. We applied this approach on a test area in the Valle d'Aosta Region (North Italy) where more than fifty percent of the territory is above 2000 m a.s.l. and extensively affected by landslides. Firstly, PSI Sentinel-1 data permitted to scan the territory and to highlight the areas characterized by the highest ground motion rates, namely Active Deformation Areas (ADA). These areas were used to derive the intensity of potential landslides in terms of magnitude. Then, for the different elements at risk (EAR) we estimated both the vulnerability, by referring to values already proposed in literature for similar working scale, and the exposure, by considering the current real estate market values of the EAR in the area. We finally derived color-scale maps showing landslide intensity and values of potential loss expressed in quantitative terms (Euros for square meters). This operational methodology can provide useful indications and outputs for landslide risk management at regional scale. Considering the present availability of Sentinel-1 SAR images with 6-days revisiting time, this procedure can represent an example of satellite InSAR monitoring as supporting tool for Civil Protection activities and geohazard mitigation long-term strategies.

Keywords

Satellite interferometry, Sentinel-1, landslide, potential worth of loss

Introduction

Landslide risk assessment is an efficient approach to mitigate geohazards and reduce potential disasters. Nevertheless, landslide risk and its components (hazard and intensity of phenomena, vulnerability and exposure of elements at risk) are still a difficult issue to address. This is especially true over large areas, where specific data about landslide occurrence and kinematics, as well as values of vulnerability and exposure are usually quite challenging to collect (Liu & Miao, 2018; Corominas et al., 2014).

In the last decade, landslide risk studies have made relevant progress and many qualitative or quantitative methods have been proposed and tested (e.g. Dai et al., 2002; van Westen et al., 2006). In this work, we assessed the impact of potential landslides on built-up areas and road networks by estimating intensity, vulnerability, exposure and potential loss on a test area in Valle

D'Aosta region (northwestern Italy). The area is characterized by steep slopes and widespread landslides.

In particular, we exploited space-borne interferometric products as starting point of an operational procedure based on the so-called ADA (Active Deformation Areas) (Barra et al., 2018; Solari et al., 2018) resulting from Persistent Scatterers Interferometry (PSI) data. PSI products were derived from Sentinel-1 radar images with the aim to provide landslide intensity as magnitude of potential slow-moving landslides (Bianchini et al., 2017). The final goal is to quantify by an economic point of view the potential worth of loss suffered by buildings or roads where the fastest motions are detected (i.e. where ADA are found). The outputs of this work are simplified colour-scale maps indicating those structures and infrastructures with a greater probability to suffer for the impact of a geohazard and those ones affected by the dynamic of an active geohazard.

Study area

Geomorphological setting

The test area of this work is the eastern portion of Valle d’Aosta, a small alpine region in north-western Italy (Fig.1). The area is mainly mountainous and characterized by four N-S oriented valleys and slopes with peaks that reach up 4000 m a.s.l. The geological/geomorphological context, the high topographic relief as well as local climatic conditions control landslide processes. Debris flows, rockslides, complex and rotational landslides as well as Deep-Seated Gravitational Slopes Deformations (DSGSD), which cover the 14% of the regional territory, are the most widespread typologies (Trigila et al., 2010; Giordan et al., 2017).

The area of interest is characterized by 972 mapped landslides and 101 DSGSD included in the IFFI catalogue (Inventario dei Fenomeni Franosi in Italia – Italian landslide inventory - Trigila et al., 2010) (Fig.1).

In the area, landslides are potential threat for the population and responsible for great economic losses. The Mont de La Saxe rockslide is an example; its activity could generate socio-economic consequences estimated in one billion of euros, involving 1200 inhabitants. Fatal events in the area were registered in October 2000 when a series of debris flows killed 17 people, or in August 2018 when two landslides caused 2 fatalities in the Val Ferret in Mont Blanc Massif (Ratto et al., 2003).

Fig. 1 Location of the Area Of Interest (AOI).

Input data

The Valle d’Aosta Region is characterized by sparse urban areas, with the largest cities, including Aosta, located along the main NW-SE oriented valley (Dora Baltea Valley). In this context, InSAR data are a valuable support for landslide investigations, offering a good

compromise between costs and spatial-temporal resolution and coverage.

Available satellite radar data over the AOI consist of 153 SAR images acquired in C-band by Sentinel-1 satellite in the period January 2015 – August 2018 in descending orbit. Radar images were processed by means of a dedicated PSI approach (Barra et al., 2017). The spatial distribution of PSI LOS (Line Of Sight) mean yearly velocities is shown in Figure 2a. Some wide moving areas related to deep-seated landslides are recognizable.

Fig. 2 (a) Sentinel-1 PSI descending data; (b) ADA database classified according to mean velocity.

The stability threshold of the velocity map was fixed at ± 5 mm/year, value equal to the standard deviation value (σ) of the dataset.

ADA were extracted from the PSI points population by following a semi-automatic procedure already proposed and tested by Barra et al. (2018) and Solari et al. (2018).

Fig. 3 Flowchart of the procedure for deriving intensity, EAR exposure and potential worth of loss.

The ADA are clusters of moving PS selected on the basis of a velocity threshold (set as 2σ where σ is the standard deviation value of the LOS velocity of the PSI dataset) and of simple spatial aggregating parameters, i.e. minimum number of PS that an ADA must contain (set as 5 PSI), and clustering radius built around every moving PS (set as 28 m, which is almost two times Sentinel-1 ground resolution).

A total number of 54 ADA clusters were detected in the AOI. In Fig.2b ADA are classified on the basis of mean velocity value, obtained by averaging the velocities of all the PS points that form each moving area. The ADA are well distributed on the territory, mostly on W-facing slopes given the satellite descending geometry. The majority of ADA records average velocities higher than 15 mm/yr (52%), while few ones show velocities higher than 25 mm/yr (8%) (Fig. 2b).

Step-by-step methodology

The methodology aims to provide the potential worth of loss (D) due to possible mass movements on the territory starting from a regional scale deformation map obtained through PSI data and ADA-derived moving areas (Fig. 3).

The landslide intensity is assessed using ADA in a dual form depending on two conditions: i) if the ADA directly overlaps an urban area (intersection with one or more buildings/roads), then it is taken as direct estimation of landslide magnitude and the landslide intensity depends on the average velocity of the ADA (ADA-related intensity); ii) if the ADA does not intersect any urban fabric, but it is found within a possible unstable debris area with presence of detrital cover, then the ADA is taken as possible source area of an unstable debris mass that could evolve into a mass movement (i.e. debris flow). In this second case, a run-out basin-scale model -Gravitational Process Path, GPP (Wichmann, 2017) - is used to evaluate the possible landslide evolution, in terms of landslide path, spatial distribution and thickness of the accumulation zone and the intensity is derived from GPP outputs (Model-related intensity). GPP is available as tool of the open source system SAGA GIS.

Once we have derived vulnerability (V), which depends on intensity and elements at risk (EAR) types,

and exposure (E), determined by considering the cadastral database and market monetary value, the potential worth of loss (D) is computed as product between V and E. The final output contains a preliminary quantitative evaluation of landslide impact and loss degree.

Results

Evaluation of landslide intensity

For the landslide intensity evaluation, ADA clusters were used as direct estimation of landslide magnitude (“ADA-related intensity”) or as an effort to detect potential source areas of moving debris masses (“Model-related intensity”).

1) ADA-related intensity

This approach relies on the overlapping between ADA and urban area/single building/road (Solari et al., 2018). Landslide intensity is here conceived as direct expression of landslide velocity (derived from LOS deformation rates of the PSI data) and thus defined by the mean velocity of the ADA, following the classification:

- intensity 1: average velocity lower than 16 mm/yr;
- intensity 2: average velocity between 16 and 32 mm/yr;
- intensity 3: average velocity higher than 32 mm/yr.

The first threshold (16 mm/yr) is representative for the passage between extremely slow and very slow landslides, as assumed by Cruden and Varnes (1996), while the second one (32 mm/yr) is obtained by doubling up the first value.

2) Model-related intensity

In the Model-related approach the ADA are both a proxy for ground moving areas and an input for the GPP model, acting as the main factor for the source areas definition. We assumed that a debris mass in correspondence of an ADA, already in motion (as testified by the PS data), could evolve into a debris flow if external triggering factors are present (i.e. an intense rainfall period). Therefore, if an ADA is found within a possible unstable debris area, defined on the basis of geological analysis and orthophoto interpretation, the

GPP run-out model is used to evaluate the possible motion along the slope, spatial distribution and thickness of the accumulation zone.

A 2m DEM was used as input for the model. The source areas were defined within each ADA and selected considering the distribution of moving points and the local morphology. For soil/debris thickness, we used the results derived within the area of interest by Salvatici et al. (2018) using the Geomorphologically Indexed Soil Thickness model (Catani et al., 2010). The height of material deposited at every cell was used as a proxy for landslide intensity. The three intensity classes are:

- intensity 1: height of material lower than 1.25 m;
- intensity 2: height of material between 1.26 and 2 m;
- intensity 3: height of material higher than 2.01 m.

The values were chosen by following the vulnerability functions derived by Papathoma-Kohle et al. (2015) considering debris flow events occurred in South Tyrol in Austria. The three intensity classes are equal to a loss degree of 30%, 60% and higher than 60%, respectively.

Evaluation of vulnerability and exposure of the elements at risk

We defined Vulnerability (V) as a parameter that varies between 0 (no damage) and 1 (complete loss). V is a function of landslide intensity. Each value of vulnerability was defined on the type of element at risk by following a data driven approach and considering the possible interactions between elements and landslide. For deriving the polygons/lines of EAR, a cadastral map at 1:2000 scale of the whole Valle D'Aosta Region was used.

The values of vulnerability assigned to each EAR typology were chosen by considering previous literature works at similar scale (Catani et al., 2005; Bianchini et al., 2017) and they are reported in Table 1.

The exposure (E) is a monetary value that was assigned to each EAR type by extracting information from various bibliographic resources (market value, construction cost, renovation cost). For private houses, E (€/m²) was determined by following the market value, as defined in the OMI (Osservatorio del Mercato Immobiliare – Real estate market observatory) managed by the Italian revenue agency (OMI, 2018).

In Table 1 the range values of E refer to the minimum and maximum value among the 35 municipalities for the AOI, while single value are unique values that are valid for all the 35 municipalities. For road categories, the E value was assigned on the basis of the construction/renovation cost for square meter.

The values of vulnerability of Table 1 are common for both the ADA-related and Model-related approaches used to evaluate the 3 landslide intensity classes I.

Table 1 Vulnerability and exposure values for the area of interest: V, vulnerability; I, intensity; E, exposure.

EAR type	V for I=1	V for I=2	V for I=3	Exposure E (€/m ²)
Barn	0.2	0.4	0.6	80
Camping	0.4	0.6	0.8	2600
Greenhouse	0.2	0.4	0.6	50
Hotel	0.15	0.3	0.5	1550 – 4600
Industry	0.1	0.2	0.5	740 – 1000
Local road	0.6	0.8	1	50
Motorway	0.4	0.6	0.8	350
Municipal road	0.6	0.8	1	150
Office/service	0.1	0.3	0.6	1175 – 2600
Private house	0.2	0.35	0.6	1075 – 4350
Provincial road	0.6	0.8	1	180
School complex	0.3	0.5	0.7	4000
Shed	0.2	0.4	0.6	540-890
Restaurant	0.2	0.35	0.6	865 – 2100
Shopping mall	0.2	0.35	0.6	1400 – 2200
Sport facilities	0.3	0.5	0.7	15-120
Stable	0.15	0.4	0.6	120
Regional road	0.4	0.6	0.8	250
Warehouse	0.2	0.4	0.6	680 - 1000

Evaluation of potential worth of loss

The potential worth of loss (D) is function of the elements at risk and vulnerability for a given intensity hazardous event. We computed D in quantitative terms (Euros for square meters) deriving it as the product between vulnerability and exposure. If one or both vulnerability or exposure are null, the potential loss is zero (Catani et al., 2005).

In Figure 4 an example of application of the ADA-related approach is shown. The site is located in the Valtournenche municipality (Chaloz hamlet) along a west-facing slope in which several landslides are already known and mapped (Fig. 4a). In particular, a large DSGSD involves the entire flank from 2900 m a.s.l. to 1500 m a.s.l. altitude (Giordan et al., 2017). Within the lower part of the deep-seated landslide, four ADAs are detected with average LOS velocities between 11 and 16 mm/year, resulting in the intensity class 1. Several hundred buildings (especially private houses warehouses and hotels) as well as some local and provincial roads are located within ADA boundaries and thus exposed to potential landslide risk.

Considering the intensity class and the type of EAR, the vulnerability ranges 0.1-0.2 for buildings and ranges 0.4-0.6 for roads. After assigning E values, the potential worth of loss varies between 21 and 490 €/m² (Fig 4b).

Fig. 4 (a) PSI data and landslide database; (b) Involved EAR classified in potential loss on Chaloz hamlet.

In Figure 5 an example of Model-related application is shown. The site is located in the Montjovet municipality (Tron hamlet). One DSSGD and two complex landslides are mapped in the landslide inventory of the area. One ADA is detected in the upper part of the complex landslides, where debris deposits are present (Figure 5a).

Starting from two source areas (traced in dashed lines and labelled as S₁ and S₂ in Figure 5b) within the ADA, the GPP model simulated the run-out of possible debris flows on the slope. The input thickness of the material deposits were 2-2.4 m and 0.6-1 m for S₁ and S₂ areas, respectively. The flows originated from these two source areas converge and create a fan-like deposit with variable thickness between 0.2 and 1.6 m, thus the resulting intensity class is 1. Possible simulated mass movements intersect two local roads as shown in Figure 5b.

In this case, by considering an exposure value of 50 €/m² and a vulnerability of 0.6, the output potential damage and worth of loss is 30 €/m² (Fig. 5b).

Fig. 5 (a) PSI data and landslide database; (b) Involved EAR classified in potential loss on Tron hamlet.

Discussion and conclusions

In this work, we proposed a procedure which starts from Sentinel-1 PSI data and leads to the estimation of potential loss experienced by one or more elements at risk (building and roads) on areas with a certain level of landslide intensity.

Given the working scale (i.e. regional, basin scale) some approximations needed to be made. The maximum level of detail about economic exposure value of buildings is obtainable from the real estate market. No further information regarding people occupancy or residency type (e.g. inhabited all-year round or rented for holiday) is collectable at this scale in a reasonable time. Furthermore, the use of the ADA database is practical and useful for rapid and semi-automatic detection of the areas characterized by the highest ground motions rates at wide scale where attention must be focused. Nevertheless, the exploitation of ADA must be carefully carried out: the ADA interpretation permits to outline the dynamics and morphological setting of a site, but it does not specifically include the recognition of landslide type or the real spatial extension of the phenomenon.

In conclusion, the outcomes of this work provide preliminary space-borne indications of the most moving areas at regional scale. This information is useful for Civil Protection entities and authorities in charge of risk

management to easily know which are the areas that are moving faster, and which is their potential impact on built-up areas.

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[Silvia Bianchini](#)

Earth Sciences Department, University of Firenze, Via La Pira 4, 50121, Florence, Italy
e-mail: silvia.bianchini@unifi.it

[Lorenzo Solari](#)

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya
Geomatics Division, 08860, Castelldefels, Spain
e-mail: lorenzo.solari@cttc.cat

[Anna Barra](#)

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya
Geomatics Division, 08860, Castelldefels, Spain
e-mail: anna.barra@cttc.cat

[Oriol Monserrat](#)

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya
Geomatics Division, 08860, Castelldefels, Spain
e-mail: oriol.monserrat@cttc.cat

[Michele Crosetto](#)

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya
Geomatics Division, 08860, Castelldefels, Spain
e-mail: michele.crosetto@cttc.cat

[Filippo Catani](#)

Earth Sciences Department, University of Firenze, Via La Pira 4, 50121, Florence, Italy
e-mail: Filippo.catani@unifi.it